

THE INFLUENCE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS AND MODERN TECHNOLOGY IN ELL

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Abstract: The twenty first century demands to live suitably to the period being aware of foreign languages and technology innovations. And this knowledge is gained through studying well with effective methods. This paper deals with the role of authentic materials and ICTs in English language learning. Accordingly, efficient ways of ELL include usage of technology facilities and authentic materials. As a consequence, in classes which these modern methods are used there will be progress in language proficiency.

Keywords: Technology, ICT, Authentic Materials, Language Proficiency

Apparently, today is the era that every field is being digitized due to the technological progress. In this modern twenty first century everything is connected with innovations of technology that is used in all walks of life. Because, it facilitates every aspect of human activity, i.e. use of modern technology can help to accomplish job faster and more efficiently rather than making on hand.

In order to live or act suitably to the present time, everyone uses facilities that are being renewed and developed day by day. As in every sphere like architecture, business, medicine, government or, also in education the role of technology is incredible. In a study process, it is significant to find an appropriate and efficient teaching method. If teacher utilizes technology tools, it can be cause to easily draw students' attention and increase their activeness during the class. In traditional classrooms, usual way of teaching is still saved and it is influencing on decrease of

students' interest in learning. Instructor stands in front of the students, near the blackboard and explains the topic using just classroom tools. Especially in language learning, it is effective to use modern methods such as information technologies (IT). Ahmadi (2017) stated that one of the important elements for learning is the method that instructors use in their classes to facilitate language learning process. Mainly foreign language learners need different methods because of that they are learning different language and they require different atmosphere apart from the native one. They can adapt their target language sphere, if there are enough sources from the internet and authentic materials in the TL. Internet facilities can motivate learners to learn more and more. Because, there are so many information to get and we can find suitable data wherever and whenever we need. In the internet, for one topic there are so many results that can show all the aspects of the topic. Presence of various and much information can make a learner interested and gives enthusiasm to receive colorful knowledge. That's why it can stimulate a student to study with a high willing for enriching their knowledge.

With English reportedly the most commonly 'learned' second language around the world (Crystal, 1997; Special Eurobarometer, 2006: 243), we can consider that it is a language of every field that is being digitized according to the modern century. Thus, there is a high progress in teaching and learning rate of English. The language is becoming a main weapon of communication and main language of technology. Therefore, there are a large number of effective methods for English learner and instructors in order to achieve language proficiency.

Moreover, one of advantageous methods is using authentic materials. Authentic materials are video, audio and print materials that students come across in daily life such as advertisements, articles we read, songs, audios we listen to or TV shows we watch. They may have an essential role in FLL that can impact on students' adaptation to the target destination. Using this method learners become more fluent and act like native speakers.

Currently the usage of media is dramatically increasing in all fields including education, especially ELL sphere. It is advantageous to conduct the lesson having colorful media that is suitable for students or according to the topic of the lesson. There are a lot of beneficial sides of utilizing media while teaching and learning English. In a process of teaching the language usage of various media tools as authentic materials can involve the whole audience into the lesson and can make them more active and enthusiastic. Murcia (2001: 461) asserts, "Media tools are physical things used by the teacher to motivate the students by bringing a slice of real life into the classroom and by presenting language in its more complete communication complex". As mentioned above, such kind of authentic materials show some real experience from the target language sphere and can make the students aware of important information about the native world of the TL.

Moreover, through the usage of modern devices that include ICT and authentic materials student can grow autonomously. Even without having a real and common lesson, learner can improve his knowledge by himself trying to search something new and useful from the internet. In one hand, utilization of technology can develop both teacher's and students' IT skills. On the other hand, it is possible that person may become addicted to the network, if there is no self-control or control by his parents or other responsible people.

To sum up, to achieve FL proficiency modern and effective methods like the ones mentioned above should be used in ELL process.

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